

Original Research

Subnational Government Expenditure and Economic Growth in Nigeria's South-South Region: A Disaggregated Approach

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Abstract

The study aims to empirically examine the contribution of subnational government expenditure to economic growth in South-South Nigeria. Existing studies on the relationship between government expenditure and economic growth yield conflicting results, primarily concentrating on developed economies and often at the central level. This study examines the functionality and composition of public spending in South-South Nigeria from 2000 to 2023. This study aims to identify the components of government expenditure that influence economic growth, utilizing panel data from South-South Nigeria to inform policy formulation. This study conducted both descriptive and econometric inferential analyses. The econometric analysis involved disaggregating total government expenditure to examine the impact of various components of public spending on economic growth. The research utilized secondary data. The study found that, overall, the effects of capital and recurrent expenditures on economic growth are minimal. Capital and recurrent expenditures have not substantially fostered economic growth across the States. Therefore, enhancing financial transparency and accountability at a subnational level is essential for optimizing growth.

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JEL classification: H76, I3

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Introduction

Government expenditure has potential impact on all economic sectors and influencing economic outcomes such as economic growth, investment, savings, among others (Efayena & Olele, 2024; Htun, 2024). Nigeria is not immune to the effects of expenditure on economic performance. Due to years of financial misappropriation, Nigeria’s economy faces rising inflation, debt, and unstable economic growth (Efayena & Olele, 2023). The Nigerian government has continued to appropriate financial resources to the various sectors of the economy. Government expenditure can be disaggregated into recurrent and capital expenditure. Recurrent expenditure covers government financial obligations in recurrent expenses such as salaries and wages, administrative and operational cost. While capital expenditure covers expenses on capital projects such as roads, bridges, and other infrastructural facilities. There is an increasing trend in both recurrent and capital expenditure through the decades. For instance, recurrent expenditure increased from ₦0.46 trillion in 2000 to ₦3.83 trillion in 2015. As at 2023, recurrent expenditure stood at ₦14.29 trillion. Whereas, capital expenditure increased from ₦0.24 trillion in 2000 to ₦8.18 trillion in 2015. As at 2023, capital expenditure stood at ₦4.49 trillion (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2023). From all indications, recurrent expenditure exceeds capital expenditure. This trend will potentially impact economic growth since capital expenditure impact economic growth (Efayena & Olele, 2020). This trend is presented in Figure 1. We observed a slump in economic growth since 2015. This situation worsened in the COVID-19 era. Recent years have experienced a rise in economic growth.

Figure 1. Disaggregated expenditure and economic growth in Nigeria (2000-2023)

Nigeria fiscal policy responsibilities are shared between the tiers of government with the central government having the largest share in revenue allocation. With return to civilian rule, the fiscal policy roles and responsibilities of subnational governments are becoming as important as that of the central government. At independence in 1960, the country is segregated into three distinct regions. The three regions are North, East and Western Regions with a federal government at the centre. The regional governments were autonomous and self-sufficient. However, the regional governments have been replaced with 36 Sub-national governments, as well as the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. The creation of more Sub-national governments followed series of successive military administrations since 1966 before the return to civilian rule in 1999.

The sub-national governments are entrusted with the responsibility of providing important public services such as road infrastructures, basic health care, social service and education. The 1999 Constitution specifically increase states' responsibilities in providing infrastructure and social amenities (services). However, there exists conflicts and ambiguity with regards to Federal and States government responsibilities in providing basic amenities as can be seen in federal government allotting education expenditure across the three tiers of government. But because of increased demand for basic education and the subsequent collapse of primary and secondary schools at the sub national levels, the federal government is constrained to intervene through the Universal Basic Education programme. In terms of revenue allocation, the sub national governments received ₦2.7 trillion in 2014 and ₦ 9,012.04 trillion between 2015 and 2019 (CBN, 2019). Despite, the accumulated revenues over the years, sub national governments have not done very well in meeting and fulfilling their responsibilities to the citizens and hence, all the indices of economic growth in the states are in the negative, with the general economy being plunged into rising debts (Efayena & Olele, 2021; Efayena & Olele, 2019). The abysmal failure of sub national governments to contribute meaningfully to economic growth may be attributed to weak institutions and endemic corruption. Also, majority of sub-national governments lacks transparency as there is little or no scrutiny of state revenues and expenditure (Adedeji, 2025; Efang et al., 2023).

With increasing role of sub-national governments in fiscal policy actions and strong theoretical presumption that over-centralized government size is likely to reduce economic growth (see, Ram 1986). Conversely, economic growth is stimulated by increased government size, thus reducing countries' dependence (Rubinson, 1977). Similarly, the Keynesian economists strongly believed that a larger government is likely going to enhance economic growth, as high level of government consumption stimulates production to match increased demand for economic goods and services. As plausible as this positive trend, there is a stimulated threshold beyond which economic growth takes a nose-dive (Barro, 1990; Armey, 1995), thus making the government size-economic growth model conspicuously undefined. Therefore, in the light of the unclear theoretical and empirical evidence, this paper provided empirical evidence on the impact of sub-national governments spending on economic growth with evidence from South-South Nigeria between 2013 and 2019. Therefore, the general objective of this study is to x-ray the effect of government expenditure on economic growth among states in South-South Nigeria. The specific objectives are; i) To ascertain the relationship between recurrent expenditure on growth in South-South Nigeria. ii) To ascertain the relationship between capital expenditure on growth in South-South Nigeria.

The approach of this study is plausible because several studies have shown that heterogeneity of expenditure may influence the extent to which expenditure influence economic growth (see Efayena et al., 2024; Efayena & Buzugbe, 2021). In other words, the impact of expenditure on economic growth may differ from the central government to sub-national government. In addition, most previous analysis was macro in nature, giving little consideration to subnational governments. Such subnational analysis can potentially present regional-specific characteristics which can direct national policies. Numerous empirical studies have been shown to lack consistency. The precise relationship between economic growth and government expenditures remains unresolved, as does the level of government spending necessary to promote economic growth. Empirical studies have yielded varying outcomes. For instance, Ebipre and Eniekezimene (2020) found that government capital expenditures exhibited an inverse relationship with RGDP in both the short run and the long run. The recurrent component exhibited a positive association with RGDP in both the long and short term. Olulu et al. (2014) demonstrate an inverse relationship between government health expenditures and economic growth.

In contrast, Yusuf et al. (2015) concluded that no components of government expenditures significantly contribute to economic growth in the short term. In the long term, government spending on defence hinders economic growth, whereas government spending on agriculture fosters it. Conversely, government spending on education and transport/communication does not exert a long-term influence on economic growth.

The contribution of this paper to the existing literature is summarized as follows. First, by using Generalized Least Squares (GLS) regression, the paper added empirical evidence on the impact of sub-national governments spending on economic growth that is free from endogeneity problems inherent in fiscal policy research. Second, to the best of our knowledge, this study may be the first of its kind on the impact of sub-national governments spending on economic growth in South-South Nigeria. The study also novel in incorporating oil revenue dependence variable in appraising the expenditure-economic growth nexus among the states.

Literature Review

Theoretical Literature

The study examined some government expenditure theories such as the *Wagner*, the *Peacock and Wiseman-Displacement*, and the *Leviathan* theories to provide a theoretical framework for the study.

Wagner Theory

The theory propounded in 1883 by German economist Adolph Wagner ranked public sector development as the key to growth. The theory opined that expenditure increases due to a country's industrial and economic growth. This theory further emphasizes that there is both an absolute and a relative expansion of the public sector at the cost of the growth in the private sector. This is rooted on the assumption that during an industrialization process, as the real income per capita of a country increase, the share of

public expenditure is also expected to increase (Lamaritina & Zaghini, 2011; Babatunde, 2011). This suggests that the development in the industrial sector of a country will be accompanied by increased government expenditure. It implies that government expenditure increases as a result of pursuing industrial and economic growth.

Bird (1971) employed three evidences in the justification of the Wagner's theory opining that government's functional roles requires huge expenditure (capital) outlay; there will be the need for increased provision of social and cultural goods and services as the industrial sector grows. Bird (1971) argued that in maintaining natural monopolies it is expected that government will increase its expenditure. In addition, such expenditure makes for the smooth operation of market forces. Thus, the Wagner's theory implied that government expenditure and industrial and economic growth moves in the same quadrant.

Peacock-Wiseman Displacement Theory

Another popular theory that explains the behaviour of government expenditure is the Peacock-Wiseman Displacement theory propounded in 1961. The theory opined that government expenditure does not follow a smooth trajectory but at discrete intervals 'jumps' owing to political instabilities in the economic system. That implies that during upheavals (political, economic and social), it is expected that government expenditure will increase accordingly. According to the three underlying assumptions of the theory, higher taxes are susceptible to individuals in a country; government is responsible for individuals' welfare; and government will tend to increase its expenditure of financial resources (Henrekson, 1993). Thus, periods of relative peace and tranquility is accompanied with a stable tax incidence and reduced government revenue. However, during periods of national political instability, the tax levels seem to increase (displaced upward) and consequently increase government expenditure.

Leviathan Theory

This theory proposes that the aggregate government's intervention in the economy will be reduced as the taxes and expenditures are reduced, *ceteris paribus*. This theory according to Rodden (2003) sprang from the conception that the central government is a 'revenue maximizing leviathan' whose main objective is maximization of revenue by fiscal decentralization of the central government monopoly on taxation. This theory maintains that the more decentralized the central government, the lower the government spending in the economy because the decentralized unit oversees revenue generation and expenditure, thus reducing the pressure on the center and the regional units becoming more accountable.

The Leviathan characteristic is portrayed in Nigeria as *fiscal hydrocephalus* (Olayiwola & Osabuohien, 2010) since the central the federal government has overbearing fiscal jurisdiction which covers the legislating, administrating and collecting of taxes. This is apparently obvious with the central government legislates over 15 types of taxes and collects 8 tax types. The state governments only legislate over 6 tax types and administer 11 tax types, while the local government, which is the lowest cadre in public administration has minimal fiscal jurisdiction, administering and collecting only two types of tax (Olayiwola & Osabuohien, 2010).

Although, the Leviathan theory has been applied in Canada and the United States (Rodden, 2003), not much evidence exists using data from developing countries like Nigeria.

Empirical Review

Several studies exist on the government expenditure-economic growth linkage, with the results ranging from negative, positive and mixed outcomes. In the Nigerian context, Christopher et al. (2025) examine the influence of government spending on economic growth in Nigeria, with an emphasis on capital and recurrent expenditures in the agriculture and infrastructure sectors. The study uses time series data spanning from 1985 to 2023 and applies the Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares (FMOLS) method. The results indicate a robust positive and statistically significant effect of expenditure on economic growth. This study corroborates previous studies such as Aluthge et al. (2021), Abu and Abdullahi (2010), among others.

Whereas other studies show a negative expenditure-growth nexus in Nigeria. For instance, Osasona et al. (2024) examine the effect of government expenditure on Nigeria's economic growth from 1986 to 2021 using the Autoregression Distributed Lag (ARDL) model. The analysis concentrated on government capital expenditure, recurrent expenditure, and total expenditure. The Gross Domestic Product (RGDP) served as a proxy for economic growth, with total capital expenditure, total recurrent expenditure, total expenditure, and domestic debt financing acting as explanatory variables. The findings indicated that total capital expenditure was both positive and statistically insignificant, as was total recurrent expenditure.

Similarly, Udude et al. (2023) examine the correlation between government expenditure and economic growth in Nigeria from 1981 to 2022. The results of the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) indicated that government recurrent expenditure and government capital expenditure have negative and significant effects on economic growth.

Other studies in Nigeria showed mixed outcomes. For instance, Chandana et al. (2020) examines the effect of Nigerian government expenditure, categorised into capital and recurrent, on economic growth through time series data spanning 1970–2019. The study uses the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model. The study incorporates structural breaks in the unit root test and co-integration analysis to enhance the robustness of results. The study's key findings indicate that capital expenditure positively and significantly influences economic growth in both the short and long term, whereas recurrent expenditure does not significantly affect economic growth in either timeframe.

Onifade et al. (2020) examines the effects of public expenditures on economic growth, focusing on capital expenditure, recurrent expenditure, and government fiscal expansion, in relation to budgetary allocations across various sectors within the Nigerian economy. Pesaran's ARDL approach has been used to conduct an impact analysis employing annual time-series data spanning from 1981 to 2017. Empirical evidence indicates a direct relationship between public spending indicators and economic growth in Nigeria. Recurrent government expenditures were found to significantly negatively impact

economic growth, while the positive effects of public capital expenditures were not significant during the study period.

Baba (2014) investigated the effectiveness of fiscal policies at the different tiers of government in Nigeria. The study found a “centripetal bias” in power allocation and expenditure structure between the tiers opining that subnational governments’ expenditure largely exceeds that of the central government although they possess low revenue capacity thus making them heavily dependent on federal government for revenue. The study find that subnational governments’ fiscal deficit has an increasing trajectory. The study recommended subnational governments’ tax base divulgence and revenue base diversification to stimulate increased expenditure.

Babatunde (2018) established that government expenditure on health, education, communication, transport and communication positively impact economic growth in Nigeria, whereas, agriculture expenditure has not significantly influenced economic growth in Nigeria between 1980 and 2016, thus prompting the study to recommend that government should re-evaluate its expenditure structure and context to achieve desired goals.

These outcomes are not peculiar to Nigeria. For instance, Htun (2024) aims to identify trends in the growth rates of government spending and GDP from 2011 to 2023, and to analyse the relationship between government spending and economic growth in Myanmar. The study found a positive correlation between economic growth and government spending in Myanmar. Government spending Granger-causes economic growth in Myanmar; however, economic growth does not Granger-cause government spending.

Okunlola et al. (2024) examines the impact of government spending on real economic growth in ECOWAS nations. This study employed panel cointegration methods to analyse the effect of government expenditures on economic growth across a sample of 15 ECOWAS nations from 1999 to 2021. The research employs POLS, FMOLS, and DOLS methodologies to estimate four distinct models. The research indicates that government spending has a positive impact on real economic growth in ECOWAS nations.

Rahman et al. (2023) examines the impact of government expenditure on economic growth in the SAARC countries. The study employed quantitative techniques, including regression, co-integration, and Granger causality, to analyse panel data from SAARC countries—Bangladesh, India, Pakistan, Sri Lanka, and Bhutan—covering the period from 2011 to 2020. The findings indicate that government spending exerts a significant positive effect on GDP in these nations. Secondly, in SAARC countries, there exists a persistent relationship between government expenditure and economic growth. In SAARC countries, a unidirectional causal relationship exists between GDP and government expenditure in the region.

Buthelezi (2023) examines the effects of long-term government spending on economic growth across various states in South Africa. This study employs vector-error correction (VEC) and Markov-switching dynamic regression methodologies, utilising data spanning from 1994 to 2021. This paper evaluates the short- and long-term effects of government

expenditure on various states of economic growth in South Africa. In South Africa, increased government expenditure has not led to economic growth, contradicting the Keynesian perspective. In both lower economic states, government expenditure diminishes economic growth by 0.009% and 0.30%. Shocks in government expenditure have been identified as harmful to economic growth. Fiscal authorities are advised to increase government expenditure in the short term rather than in the long term while also monitoring such expenditures.

Arawatari et al. (2023) analyses the relationship between productive government spending and economic growth. The research calibrated data from the United States. The nexus between the government expenditure-to-GDP ratio and the economic growth rate is represented by an inverted U-shaped curve with a flat apex. The flat peak of the curve suggests that variations in government expenditure size exert a constrained influence on economic growth. The theoretical and numerical findings indicate that discussions regarding the correlation between government size and economic growth may be misguided, except in cases where government size is either significantly large or small.

Poku et al. (2022) analyses the effect of government expenditure on economic growth in Ghana, utilising data from 1970–2016 and applying the ARDL econometric estimation technique. Empirical findings indicate that government expenditure positively correlates with economic growth in the short run. The findings indicate that foreign direct investment and gross capital formation exhibit a significant positive association with economic growth in both the short run and long run. The investment outcome was similar with the study of Efayena et al. (2024) which analyses the impact of military expenditure on economic growth in sub-Saharan Africa.

Olaoye et al. (2020) investigates the asymmetrical relationship between government spending and economic growth within the ECOWAS region. This study employs the System Generalised Method of Moments in the context of panel data analysis, effectively addressing the potential endogeneity of fiscal variables by utilising internal instruments and distinguishing between negative and positive shocks to government spending. The study employs Driscoll and Kraay's nonparametric covariance matrix estimator to address cross-section dependency and cross-country heterogeneity present in empirical modelling. The findings indicate evidence of asymmetry in the relationship between government spending and economic growth in ECOWAS during the study period. The study indicates that the impact of government spending shocks on economic growth varies based on the characteristics of the shocks themselves. This study was corroborated by Efayena et al. (2024a). Furthermore, the cumulative impact of expansionary government spending shocks on economic growth is both positive and statistically significant. The cumulative effect of contractionary government spending has a negative and statistically significant impact on economic growth. The study identified substantial evidence supporting an inverted "U-shaped" relationship between government spending and economic growth.

Sungchan and Soyoung (2020) which investigated the impact of government capital expenditure on economic growth within an endogenous growth model. The study employed a panel data analysis using data from the United States between 1990 and 2013.

Empirical results showed that capital expenditure negatively relate to growth, leading to the conclusion that capital expenditure is not an effective fiscal policy instrument.

Government expenditure influences on economic growth components in South Africa was examined in the study of Iwegbunam and Robinson (2019). Employing the cointegration model, long run estimates and the VECM techniques within Solow neoclassical growth framework, the study found a long run relationship among the variables. Specifically, the study found aggregate private consumption expenditure impact negatively on economic growth. The study concluded by recommending that efforts should be focused on efficient monitoring of government expenditure as well as increases expenditure on labour and capital development.

In the same vein, the Panel Vector Auto Regression (PVAR) was employed by Srithongrungrung and Kriz (2014) to avoid inherent endogeneity issues in the investigation of United States subnational economic growth-fiscal policies nexus. The point estimates of the personal income responses to fiscal policy shocks obtained from impulse response table and graphs indicated that taxes have a negative effect on income growth in approximately a one-half ratio. In addition to current year effect, this tax effect is only a year lagged and is transient, rather than persistent. Operational spending has a positive effect on growth approximately at about a one-to-one ratio. Public capital spending demonstrates a positive effect on economic growth for two years after the investment occurs. The effect is more than a one-to-one ratio and lasts for three years including current year. Fiscal policies appear to have a contemporaneous effect on subnational economic growth.

Other studies showed a positive relationship between expenditure and growth. Such studies included Olaoye et al. (2020) which investigated the government expenditure-economic growth nexus among 15 ECOWAS countries over the period of 2005–2017 with special emphasis on the role of institutional environment, utilizing the generalized method of moments-system method which addresses the problem of dynamic endogeneity and found a positive impact. The study established that quality of institutions is a *sin qua non* for government spending effectiveness. Thus, the study recommended that countries should strengthen and improve the quality of government institutions in their respective countries.

Pula and Elshani (2018) carried out a study to evaluate the nature and direction of economic growth and government spending in Kosovo using 2002-2015 database. Employing an endogenous growth model, a positive relationship was established. While Ewetan et al. (2016) employed a multivariate VAR model in establishing the cause and direction of the fiscal decentralization-economic growth relationship in Nigeria. Using data of 1970 to 2012, the study established evidence of a long-run positive relationship with causality emanating a fiscal decentralization-economic growth trajectory. The study recommended strengthening the fiscal base of the state and local governments and increase further the level of fiscal decentralization. The study also recommended harmonization of constitutional issue of fiscal powers among the three tiers of government.

Contrary to the above studies, several studies had mixed findings. For instance, Nyasha and Odhiambo (2019) carried out a qualitative study by examining existing literature with a goal to establishing government size-economic growth causality. Their study showed that the direction of causality between government size and economic growth has four possible outcomes, and that all the outcomes were found to have empirical support, based on variations in the country or region under study, methodology, proxies, data set used, and time frame considered. Their exercise placed more emphasis on an economic growth-government size unidirectional granger causality. This was closely followed by a bidirectional relationship making the debate far from clear-cut.

Srithongrung and Sánchez-Juárez (2015) investigated the effects of taxes and public investment on economic growth of 32 Mexican states between 1993 and 2011. Accounting for cointegration effects and both long-term trends in the variables, the study found that taxes exerted negative effect on growth and the effect can be seen in both transitory and permanent manners, while public investment positively stimulated subnational growth in the short- and long-run, even though economic growth was not significantly affected by foreign investment. On the other hand, the paper found out that educational accomplishment negatively relates to growth. Appropriate fiscal policy-mix between taxes and public investment is thus essential in Mexico.

While Gisore et al. (2014) employed East Africa economic growth and government expenditure data of 1980 to 2010 in a panel analysis. The study found that expenditures on health and defense positively influence economic growth, while expenditures on education and agriculture do not. It is thus, imperative to suggest that more resources should be channeled to health and defence sectors than other sectors. Jin and Zou (2002) investigated fiscal decentralization measures effect on government size both at the center and subnational levels. The study adopted an econometric analysis using panel data from 32 industrial and developing countries between 1980 and 1994. The study found that expenditure decentralization results in reduced central government spending and increased subnational government spending; revenue decentralization will result in increased subnational government spending than the central government; and vertical imbalances result in increased spending at all levels of government.

A review of the literature reveals a dearth in studies that analyze the impact government spending on economic growth at the sub-national level. Such analysis will help capture heterogeneity in government spending. This study aptly captures the impact utilizing recurrent and capital expenditure components.

Methodology

This section presented the theoretical framework as well as the methods employed by the study in order to ascertain the impact of sub-national governments spending on economic growth: Evidence from South-South Nigeria.

Theoretical Framework

This study adopted the model of Devarajan et al. (1996). The choice was basically prompted by the advantage the model has over others. The model does not form an a

priori of government expenditure and can be adopted for any economic units including municipalities, countries, states, etc. The model shows that there are two forms of government spending; productive and unproductive. It also proposes that the (re)allocation of government spending determines the growth rate of the unit(s). The model assumes that are three basic factors in the growth model; private stock of capital (k); productive government spending (g_1) and unproductive government spending (g_2). The model can be expressed in constant elasticity of substitution (CES) form as:

$$y = f(k, g_1, g_2) = [Jk^{-\eta} + \mu g_1^{-\eta} + \pi g_2^{-\eta}]^{\frac{1}{\eta}} \quad (1)$$

Where;

$$\eta > 0, \mu \geq 0, \pi \geq 0, \eta + \mu + \pi = 1, \eta \geq -1$$

Government expenditure is given as equation (3) according to Barro (1990);

$$\delta y = g_1 + g_2 \quad (2)$$

Where;

$$g_1 = \psi \delta y, g_2 = (1 - \psi) \delta y, 0 \leq \psi \leq 1 \quad (3)$$

Given the scenario above, an economic agent maximizes utility in a consumption function with the function below;

$$U = \int_0^{\infty} U(C) e^{-\rho t} dt \quad (4)$$

Subject to:

$$\dot{k} = (1 - \delta)y - c \quad (5)$$

Where ρ is the given intertemporal discount rate. Faced with a given level of risk, the economic agent will strive to maximize a constant relative risk aversion (CRRA) utility function as the one given below;

$$U(C) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{1-\Omega} c^{1-\Omega} & \text{if } \Omega > 0, \Omega \neq 1 \\ \ln c & \text{if } \Omega = 1 \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

When equation (6) is substituted in equation (4) and is maximized subject to equations (1)- (3) and (5), the consumption growth equation below is obtained:

$$\frac{\dot{c}}{c} = \frac{J(1-\delta) \left\{ J + \left(\frac{g}{k}\right)^{-\eta} [\mu \psi^{\eta} + \pi (1-\psi)^{-\eta}] \right\}^{\frac{1+\eta}{\eta}} - \rho}{\Omega} \quad (7)$$

In a steady state, g/k is assumed constant, thus, its expression can be given as;

$$\frac{g}{k} = \frac{\{[\delta^\eta - \mu\psi - \pi(1 - \psi)^{-\eta}]\}^{\frac{1}{\eta}}}{J} \quad (8)$$

When we substitute the above equation into equation (7), we obtain growth rate in consumption given as;

$$\lambda = \frac{J(1 - \delta) \left\{ \frac{J\delta^\eta}{[\delta^\eta - \mu\psi^\eta - \pi(1 - \psi)^{-\eta}]^{\frac{1+\eta}{\eta}}} \right\}^{\frac{1+\eta}{\eta}} + \rho}{\Omega} \quad (9)$$

The relationship between the government productive spending and steady growth state can be obtained by differentiating equation (9) in respect to ψ as given below:

$$\frac{d\lambda}{d\psi} = \frac{J(1 - \delta)(1 + \eta)[J\delta^\eta]^{\frac{1+\eta}{\eta}} [\mu\psi^{(1+\eta)} - \pi(1 - \psi)^{-(1+\eta)}]}{\Omega[\delta^\eta - \mu\psi^{-\eta} - \pi(1 - \psi)^{-\eta}]^{\frac{1}{\eta}}} \quad (10)$$

Equation (10) implies that growth is stimulated by productive spending. In other words, when resources are efficiently allocated, it results in economic growth in the economic unit (municipalities, states, countries, etc). In addition, the impact of productive spending on economic growth also depends on its initial composition.

Although Equation (3) forms the framework of this study, one challenge faced by subnational government data is the aggregation of expenditure into productive and non-productive components. The study thus focuses on the capital and recurrent expenditure components in relation to economic growth in order to ascertain the impact of these components on economic growth of the states in South-South Nigeria.

Consequently, state governments' expenditure can be considered advantageous for influencing growth. Equation (11) is specified by expressing equation (10) as a Cobb-Douglas production function:

$$GDPG_{it} = A(RE_{it}^{\alpha_1})(CE_{it}^{\alpha_2})(OILR_{it}^{\alpha_3})(IGRG_{it}^{\alpha_4})(MI_{it}^{\alpha_5}) \quad (11)$$

Where $RGDP$, RE , CE , $OILR$, $IGRG$, and MI represent gross domestic product growth, recurrent expenditure, capital expenditure, oil revenue, and misery index. In addition, i and t represents states and time period, respectively; and

$$\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \alpha_3 + \alpha_4 + \alpha_5 < 1$$

The study uses the Panel Autoregressive Distributed Lag (PARDL) model to evaluate the impact of expenditures on economic growth. This method was selected for its capacity to manage both short-term and long-term dynamics, while also tackling issues like endogeneity and autocorrelation that are prevalent in panel data analysis (Shaari et al., 2023; Pesaran & Shin, 1999). Panel data integrates cross-sectional and time-series

observations, providing a robust analytical framework, though it presents distinct challenges. Linearizing equation (11) and adding an error term e_{it} , the model is expressed in an econometric form:

$$\ln GDPG_{it} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 RE_{it} + \alpha_2 CE_{it} + \alpha_3 OILR_{it} + \alpha_4 IGRG_{it} + \alpha_5 MI_{it} + e_{it} \quad (12)$$

Where e_{it} is the error term for state i at period t , $\alpha_0 = \ln(A)$ where A_i is level of technology and with an assumption of a constant technology, α_0 is constant, representing the model's intercept. $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \alpha_4$, and α_5 are the slopes of explanatory variables, while the *a priori* expectations are $\alpha_1 - \alpha_4 > 0$; and $\alpha_5 < 0$.

The ARDL model includes both lagged dependent and independent variables, facilitating the analysis of dynamic relationships. The PARDL model combines short-term dynamics with long-term equilibrium within a unified framework. The incorporation of lagged variables and the Error Correction Term (ECT) enhances robustness by addressing mixed integration orders (I(0) and I(1)), endogeneity, and limitations associated with small sample sizes (Haug, 2002; Pesaran et al., 2001). The panel ARDL model is expressed in equation (13):

$$GDPG_{it} = \alpha_0 + \sum_{j=0}^p \alpha_1 \Delta GDPG_{it-j} + \sum_{j=0}^q \alpha_2 \Delta RE_{it-j} + \sum_{j=0}^r \alpha_3 \Delta CE_{it-j} + \sum_{j=0}^s \alpha_4 \Delta OILR_{it-j} + \sum_{j=0}^m \alpha_5 \Delta IGRG_{it-j} + \sum_{j=0}^n \alpha_6 \Delta MI_{it-j} + e_{it} \quad (13)$$

The panel Error Correction Mechanism (ECM) facilitates the measurement of the speed of adjustment towards long-term equilibrium. The error term facilitates the correction of any short-term deviations from long-term equilibrium. The ECM is expressed in equation (14) as follows:

$$GDPG_{it} = \alpha_0 + \sum_{j=0}^p \alpha_1 \Delta GDPG_{it-j} + \sum_{j=0}^q \alpha_2 \Delta RE_{it-j} + \sum_{j=0}^r \alpha_3 \Delta CE_{it-j} + \sum_{j=0}^s \alpha_4 \Delta OILR_{it-j} + \sum_{j=0}^m \alpha_5 \Delta IGRG_{it-j} + \sum_{j=0}^n \alpha_6 \Delta MI_{it-j} + \beta_1 GDPG_{it-1} + \beta_2 RE_{it-1} + \beta_3 CE_{it-1} + \beta_4 OILR_{it-1} + \beta_5 IGRG_{it-1} + \beta_6 MI_{it-1} + e_{it} \quad (14)$$

where $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ and $t = 1, 2, \dots, t$. Δ represents the first difference, $it-1$ denotes the lagged values of the variables, α_0 is the intercept, and α_1 through α_6 are the coefficients of the variables to be estimated in the short term, while β_1 through β_6 represent the long-term coefficients. The lag length for the dependent variable is denoted as p , whereas p, q, r, s, m , and n represent the lag lengths for the independent variables, which are established through information criteria such as AIC and SBIC.

The Error Correction Term (ECT) captures the rate of adjustment towards long-term equilibrium. The error term facilitates the correction of any short-term deviations from

long-term equilibrium. This value represents a deviation from the long-run relationship, which is anticipated to be rectified over time. After establishing a long-run relationship between the dependent and independent variables, the panel ECM is represented by equation (15) and is expressed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 GDPG_{it} = & \alpha_0 + \sum_{j=0}^p \alpha_1 \Delta GDPG_{it-j} + \sum_{j=0}^q \alpha_2 \Delta RE_{it-j} + \sum_{j=0}^r \alpha_3 \Delta CE_{it-j} + \sum_{j=0}^s \alpha_4 \Delta OILR_{it-j} \\
 & + \sum_{j=0}^m \alpha_5 \Delta IGRG_{it-j} + \sum_{j=0}^n \alpha_6 \Delta MI_{it-j} + \theta ECT_{it-1} + e_{it} \quad (15)
 \end{aligned}$$

In this context, Δ denotes the first difference of the variables, while θ indicates the speed of adjustment for the coefficient of the Error Correction Term (ECT). For the long-term sustainability of the relationship, the ECT coefficient must be both significant and negative.

Preliminary Tests

Unit Root Tests

Next, time series properties of the variables were investigated. However, the number of observations in the study necessitated the use of panel unit root tests in order to minimise the risk of spurious regression estimates and structural breaks. The study employed the Levin, et al (2002) test. This test is highly appropriate for heterogeneous panels of moderate size with fixed effects and assumes that there is a common unit root process.

This test implements, basically, an ADF regression:

$$\Delta y_{it} = \xi_i y_{it-1} + \sum_{j=1}^{p_i} \vartheta_{ij} \Delta y_{it-j} + \tau_{zi} \omega_{zt} + \epsilon_{it} \quad (13)$$

Where: i is the cross-units of the panel; t refers to the time series observations; j is lag orders; τ_{zi} is vector of deterministic variables and ω_{zi} refers to the corresponding vector of coefficients for a particular model.

Variables and Scope of Study

Largely owing to dearth of economic data at the sub-national governments' level in Nigeria, the study is constrained within data of recurrent expenditure (RE), capital expenditure (CE) and gross domestic product (GDP) between 2000 and 2023. The expenditure components employed were measured as a ratio of Gross Domestic Product (GDP), while growth was captured by growth in GDP. The study also adopted two control variables. These are internal generated revenue growth (IGRG) and misery index (MI). The misery index is simply the sum of unemployment, inflation and bank lending rate less percentage change in real GDP per capita (Ekpo, 2016). The inclusion of capital expenditure, recurrent expenditure, and GDP growth was informed by previous studies (see Efayena & Olele, 2023; Ewetan et al., 2016; Efayena & Buzugbe, 2021). The

inclusion of internally generated revenue and misery index in the study was informed by studies such as Ekpo (2016), Nyasha and Odhiambo (2019) and, Jin and Zou (2002). These variables matter for short-run and long-run economic growth.

Results

This section outlines the empirical results, beginning with pre-estimation tests, which encompass the descriptive statistics of the variable series, unit root tests, and the selection of lag length for model estimation.

Descriptive Statistics

We present the descriptive statistics of the series adopted in the variables of interest. The variables include recurrent expenditure (RE), capital expenditure (CE), oil revenue (OILR), economic growth (GDPG), internal generated revenue growth (IGRG) and misery index (MI). The result of the descriptive test is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics

	LCE	LCE	LOILR	LGDPG	LIGRG	LMI
Mean	3.410	4.472	5.034	6.642	4.553	4.117
Median	3.408	4.448	5.013	6.596	4.584	4.063
Maximum	3.822	4.873	6.171	7.045	5.361	4.659
Minimum	2.963	3.768	3.403	5.624	3.574	3.511
Std. Dev.	0.206	0.215	0.548	0.539	0.439	0.310
Skewness	-0.127	-0.227	-0.511	0.074	-0.504	0.005
Kurtosis	2.438	3.067	3.405	2.055	2.273	2.437
Jarque-Bera	2.045	1.454	7.647	4.163	7.835	1.463
Prob.	0.346	0.467	0.032	0.108	0.013	0.436

From Table 1, the results show that the measures of central tendency (mean and median) display moderate values. The mean values range between 3.410 (LCE) and 6.642 (LGDPG), while the median is between 3.408 (LCE) and 6.596 (LGDPG). Also, the minimum and the maximum values reveal absence of outlier in the dataset. Also, the measure of dispersion (standard deviation) has low value. The standard deviation values range between 0.206 (LCE) and 0.548 (LOILR).

Based on the normality assumption evaluated through the Jarque-Bera statistic, which incorporates skewness and kurtosis, Table 1 indicates that all series within the variables exhibit normal distribution at both the 1 per cent and 5 per cent levels of significance. Internally generated revenue growth (IGRG) and oil revenue (OILR) exhibit a normal distribution at 1 per cent, whereas the other variables are normally distributed at 5 per cent, as indicated by the probability values. The fundamental aspect of assessing the validity of the normality assumption lies in the reliance of various statistical tests, such as the chi-square, t-statistic, and F-statistic, on the premise that the variables' distributions adhere to normality for their results to be considered valid.

Panel Unit Root

There is need to check the characteristics of the data employed. The Levin-Lin-Chu unit root test results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Panel Unit Root

Variable	Description	Statistic	p-value
RE	Unadjusted t	-23.0672	
	Adjusted t*	-24.4504	0.0000
CE	Unadjusted t	-8.3171	
	Adjusted t*	-7.4600	0.0000
GDPG	Unadjusted t	-1.1e+02	
	Adjusted t*	-1.2e+02	0.0000
IGRG	Unadjusted t	-11.0251	
	Adjusted t*	-9.3417	0.0000
MI	Unadjusted t	-21.0038	
	Adjusted t*	-19.8205	0.0000
OILR	Unadjusted t	-24.0341	
	Adjusted t*	-21.7495	0.0000

Note: statistically significant to the 1 percent level of significance

The p-value of the variables in the Levin–Lin–Chu bias-adjusted t statistic shows that all variables are significant. Therefore, the study rejects the null hypothesis and conclude that the series are stationary.

Lag length determination

Determining the required lag length is essential for the adoption of the Panel Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag (PARDL) estimation technique. Table 3 presents the test result for the optimal lag length selection criterion.

Table 3. Optimal lag length selection

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SIC	HQ
0	-24.7641	NA	0.1321	0.7356	0.8621	0.7841
1	136.3205	302.2475*	0.0037*	-3.2954*	-3.1488*	-3.2172*
2	137.0417	1.2436	0.0039	-3.2885	-3.0875	-3.2086
3	138.2934	2.4042	0.0036	-3.2943	-3.0762	-3.2001
4	138.4872	0.5628	0.0035	-3.2775	-3.0453	-3.1725
5	139.1436	0.6118	0.0038	-3.2674	-2.9755	-3.1503

Note: * denotes lag order; LR, FPE, AIC, SC, and HQ denote sequential modified LR test, Final Prediction Error, Akaike Information Criterion, Schwarz Information Criterion, and Hanna-Quinn Information Criterion, respectively.

From table 4, the lag length of 1 is obtained, following the result of different criterion such as Final prediction error (FPE), Akaike information criterion (AIC), Schwarz information (SC) and HannaQuinn (HQ) information criterion. This implies that in the

proposed Panel ARDL technique of estimation, the optimal lag length adopted is 1. This necessitates the importance of testing the long-term relationship among the variables.

Panel cointegration tests

The Pedroni test is utilised to conduct a panel cointegration analysis. This study aims to investigate the long-run relationship between economic growth and its explanatory variables. The panel cointegration test holds significance for policy implications. This allows for the prediction of future economic performance. Table 4 presents the results below.

Table 4. Cointegration tests

	Intercept and trend		Without intercept and trend	
	t-statistic	p-value	t-statistic	p-value
Panel v-statistic	-5.8375	1.0000	-3.8602	1.0000
Panel rho-statistic	4.1711	1.0000	2.5137	0.8587
Panel PP-statistic	-53.8346***	0.0000	-23.0548***	0.0000
Panel ADF-statistic	-7.0965***	0.0000	-9.1768***	0.0000
Group rho-statistic	7.4813	1.0000	4.5326	1.0000
Group PP-statistic	-31.0478***	0.0000	-27.4015***	0.0000
Group ADF-statistic	-11.2664***	0.0000	-8.4871***	0.0000

The cointegration test results from the panel indicate that out of the seven dimensions analysed, four reject the null hypothesis of no cointegration, supporting the alternative hypothesis of cointegration. Thus, in the South-South region, a long-run association exists between economic growth and its explanatory variables.

Effects of Government Spending on Economic Growth

Long run analysis

The long run results in the first segment of Table 5 reveal that capital expenditure have a positive and statistically significant effect on economic growth at 5 per cent level of significance. When government spending increases by 1 per cent, the growth of the economy increases by 0.415 per cent. On the other hand, recurrent expenditure has a positive but statistically insignificant effect on economic growth. Internally generated revenue has a positive and statistically significant effect on economic growth at 1 per cent level of significance. When internally generated revenue increases by 1 per cent, the growth of the economy increases by 0.071 per cent. In the same vein, oil revenue has a positive and statistically significant effect on economic growth at 10 per cent level of significance. When oil revenue increases by 1 per cent, the growth of the economy increases by 0.205 per cent.

Table 5. P-ARDL estimates

Method: ARDL	Dependent variable:	D(LGDPG)	
Dynamic regressors:	LGDPD (-1) LCE LIGRG LOILR LRE		
Selected Model:	ARDL (1, 1, 1, 1)	Fixed regressors: LMI C	
	Coefficient	Std. error	
<u>Long run equation</u>			
LGDPG	0.0163***	0.0024	
LCE	0.4157**	0.1360	
LIGRG	0.0705***	0.0124	
LOILR	0.2294*	0.1153	
LRE	0.2053	0.1873	
<u>Short run equation</u>			
COINTEQ01	-0.3274***	0.0674	
LGDPG	0.1058**	0.0342	
LCE	0.0619*	0.0326	
LIGRG	0.0387	0.0353	
LMI	-0.1593**	0.0487	
LOILR	0.0837*	0.0421	
LRE	0.1726*	0.0909	
C	0.5715***	0.0637	
Mean dependent var	0.0183	S.D. dependent var	0.0402
S.E. of regression	0.0349	Akaike info criterion	-4.5802
Sum squared resid	0.0469	Schwarz criterion	-2.7471
Log likelihood	391.7043	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-3.8043

Short run results

The short run results in the second segment of Table 5 show that the coefficients of cointegration or the error correction term (COINTEQ01) is statistically significant at 10 per cent and negative. The negative sign indicates a backward movement toward long run equilibrium from short run disequilibrium and the speed of adjustment is about 32%. Also, the misery index [D(LMI)] which has negative and statistically significant effect on economic growth implies that misery index has positive effect on economic growth. A 1 per cent increase in misery index will decrease economic growth by 0.1593 per cent. In addition, capital expenditure and recurrent expenditure have a positive effect on economic growth at 10% statistical significance level. Also, internally generated revenue and oil revenue have a positive effect on economic growth, but internally generated revenue has statistically insignificant effect on economic growth.

The study's finding that the expenditure components positively impact economic growth corroborates previous studies (e.g., Olaoye et al., 2020; Gisore et al., 2014; Iwegbunam & Robinson, 2019; Onifade et al., 2020). However, this study differs significantly from the previous studies since it incorporates oil revenue into its analysis. In addition, previous disaggregated analysis did not appraise the expenditure-growth nexus utilizing states dataset. Rather, previous studies centered on disaggregated macro-data. Even though the results showed that capital expenditure positively and significantly

impact economic growth in the states, the impact is infinitesimal. This is highly poor given huge capital expenditure in states in South-South Nigeria. That means that the various state governments' capital expenditure on items such as social and community services and other capital projects has not impact on economic growth in proportion to revenues inflows. The recurrent expenditure was also found to be positive but the effect is not highly significant in relation to economic growth. This implies that expenditure on education, health, defence, internal security, debt servicing and other economic services has not highly affected economic growth in the various states in South-South Nigeria.

Conclusion and Policy Implications

The paper investigated the impact of sub-national governments spending on economic growth: Evidence from South-South Nigeria between 2000 and 2023. The panel ARDL regression was used for the analysis. The empirical evidence indicates that both recurrent and capital expenditures positively impact economic growth in South-South Nigeria, with capital expenditure having a more pronounced effect. This observation is consistent with endogenous growth theory and the Keynesian fiscal framework, which highlight the long-term productivity benefits of investments in infrastructure and capacity building. Recurrent spending maintains human capital and ensures the functionality of government services, whereas capital expenditure broadens the economy's productive capacity by improving infrastructure, lowering transaction costs, and drawing in private investment. This conclusion highlights the necessity for state governments to adjust budget allocations towards high-impact capital projects that diversify the regional economy beyond oil dependence, while also ensuring sufficient recurrent funding for maintenance and service delivery. This necessitates the implementation of integrated medium-term expenditure planning, efficiency audits, and focused public-private partnerships to convert fiscal expenditures into sustainable and inclusive economic growth. Recurrent expenditure, encompassing salaries, administrative costs, and operational expenses, is crucial for sustaining government functions, maintaining public assets, and ensuring the effective deployment of human capital. Without a strong foundation of capital investment, the productivity gains from recurrent expenditure might face limitations. Paying teachers' salaries (recurrent spending) will have a greater impact if the educational system is supported by adequate school buildings, modern equipment, and reliable electricity (capital assets). The interplay between recurrent and capital spending highlights their complementary nature rather than substitutive roles, as capital expenditure establishes a basis for more efficient and effective recurrent spending.

These findings indicate the necessity for a strategic reallocation of expenditure composition in South-South states from a policy standpoint. The fiscal planning process must prioritise high-quality, growth-enhancing capital projects that mitigate structural bottlenecks in economic diversification. Due to the region's reliance on oil revenues, capital expenditure priorities must encompass infrastructure that enhances value addition in agriculture, manufacturing, tourism, and renewable energy. Investments in rural-urban connectivity, including roads, bridges, and transport hubs, can mitigate post-harvest losses in agriculture and facilitate access to interior markets for trade. Investment in industrial clusters, free trade zones, and ICT infrastructure can effectively attract private investment and enhance the region's integration into global value chains.

The pursuit of increased capital expenditure requires a balance with sufficient recurrent allocations for operations and maintenance. Subnational governments in Nigeria frequently initiate prominent capital projects that decline within a few years due to inadequate maintenance funding. A newly constructed health facility necessitates ongoing expenditures for medical staff salaries, equipment maintenance, and utility costs to maintain operational functionality. The absence of this balance will lead to a decline in the economic returns from capital expenditures over time. This study indicates the necessity for the institutionalisation of Medium-Term Expenditure Frameworks (MTEFs) to guarantee that capital projects are supported by feasible and sustainable recurrent budgets for their maintenance.

Three complementary actions are necessary to translate these findings into development outcomes. Improving fiscal efficiency is crucial; governments must enhance procurement systems, perform regular value-for-money audits, and implement transparent budgeting processes to minimise leakages and ensure that capital funds are used for their intended purposes. Integrating capital expenditure into regional growth strategies aligns public investment with broader economic diversification objectives. This entails identifying strategic sectors where public infrastructure can stimulate private investment, including agro-processing hubs, tourism corridors, and logistics centres associated with ports and airports. Third, utilising public-private partnerships (PPPs) can optimise limited public resources, enabling governments to execute large-scale infrastructure projects without excessively straining their budgets. Well-structured public-private partnerships in transportation, energy, and housing can enhance capital formation and allocate specific operational risks to the private sector. Policymakers should, therefore, adopt a balanced but strategically inclined approach that enhances capital spending, ensures the functionality of public assets through sufficient recurrent funding, and aligns fiscal decisions with a coherent, forward-looking development strategy. Through this approach, South-South states can transform fiscal expenditures into sustained, inclusive, and diversified economic growth.

Despite the importance of this study's findings, there are several limitations. The study only covers data from 2000 to 2023. These were the only available data published by government authorities. Gathering data at the sub-national level is generally difficult to compile and compute. Despite the data limitation, the study contains valuable economic inferences since the panel data analysis takes into consideration these factors. Future studies can expand on the scope of this study with availability of updated data. Future studies can also include sector-specific expenditure (e.g., health, education) or the role of institutional quality on economic growth on geopolitical basis.

References

- Abu, N., & Abdullahi, U. (2010). Government expenditure and economic growth in Nigeria, 1970-2008: A disaggregated analysis. *Business and Economics Journal*, 1-11.
- Adedeji, A. (2025). The challenges of corrupt practices and its implication on good governance in Nigeria. *Journal of Techno-Social*, 17(1), 35-45.

- Aluthge, C., Jibir, A., & Abdu, M. (2021). Impact of government expenditure on economic growth in Nigeria, 1970-2019. *Central Bank of Nigeria Journal of Applied Statistics*, 12(1), 139-174.
- Arawatari, R., Hori, T., & Mino, K. (2023). Government expenditure and economic growth: A heterogeneous-agents approach. *Journal of Macroeconomics*, 75, 103486. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmacro.2022.103486>
- Arney, D. (1995). *The Freedom Revolution*. Regnery Publishing Co., Washington, D.C.
- Baba, Y. N. (2014). Fiscal policy in Nigeria: An appraisal of the increasing role of sub-national governments. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 5(10), 28-39.
- Babatunde, M. A. (2011). A bound testing analysis of Wagner's law in Nigeria: 1970-2006. *Applied Economics*, 43(21), 2843-2850. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00036840903425012>
- Babatunde, S. A. (2018). Government spending on infrastructure and economic growth in Nigeria. *Economic Research-Ekonomska Istraživanja*, 31(1), 997-1014. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1331677X.2018.1436453>
- Barro, R. J. (1990). Government spending in a simple model of endogenous growth. *The Journal of Political Economy*, 98(5), 103-125. <https://doi.org/10.1086/261726>
- Bird, R. M. (1971). Wagner's law of expanding state activity. *Public Finance*, 26, 1-26.
- Buthelezi, E. M. (2023). Impact of government expenditure on economic growth in different states in South Africa. *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23322039.2023.2209959>
- Central Bank of Nigeria (2019). *Statistical Bulletin*. CBN Statistics Department, Abuja, Nigeria.
- Chandana, A., Adamu, J., & Musa, A. (2020). Impact of government expenditure on economic growth in Nigeria, 1970-2019. *Central Bank of Nigeria Journal of Applied Statistics*, 11(2), 139-174.
- Christopher, N., Akpan, M. S., & Ologunla, S. E. (2025). Impact of government expenditure on economic growth in Nigeria: A time series analysis of capital and recurrent expenditures in agriculture and infrastructure sectors. *South Asian Journal of Social Studies and Economics*, 22(5), 44-60. <https://doi.org/10.9734/sajsse/2025/v22i51009>
- Devarajan, S., Swarrop, V., & Zou, H-F. (1996). The composition of public expenditure and economic growth. *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 37(2), 313-344. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-3932\(96\)90039-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-3932(96)90039-2)

- Ebipre, P., & Eniekezimene, F. (2020). Government expenditure and economic growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Business & Law Research*, 8(3), 63-71.
- Efanga, J. I., Okon, U., & Umoh, U. E. (2023). Effects of economic governance on socio economic development in Nigeria. *Journal of Contemporary Issues in Accounting*, 4(1), 24-39.
- Efayena O. O., & Buzugbe, P. N. (2021). Is the heterogeneity of expenditure relevant to economic growth? The case of Nigeria. *CBN Bullion*, 45(4), 31-42.
- Efayena, O. O., & Olele, E. H. (2019). The debt-growth nexus in Nigeria: An ARDL approach. *The West African Economic Review*, 6(2), 1-29.
- Efayena, O. O., & Olele, E. H. (2020). *A validation of the Phillips Curve hypothesis in Nigeria: A quarterly data-based approach*. MPRA Paper No. 98804.
- Efayena, O. O., & Olele, E. H. (2021). Debt-economic growth nexus: Empirical evidence from South-South states of Nigeria. *Acta Universitatis Danubius. Economica*, 17(2), 7-18.
- Efayena, O. O., & Olele, E. H. (2023). Rethinking the “Phillips curve” in Nigeria: Assessing the unemployment-inflation nexus in a non-linear framework. *CBN Bullion*, 47(1), 65-74.
- Efayena, O. O., & Olele, E. H. (2024). Analysis of the relationship between military expenditure and investment in the Economic Community of West African States: A heterogeneous panel data approach. *Studia Universitatis “Vasile Goldis” Arad. Economics Series*, 34(4), 58-77. <https://doi.org/10.2478/sues-2024-0018>
- Ekpo, A. H. (2016). Global economic crisis and Africa’s economic performance. *Africa Insight*, 46(1), 9-33.
- Ewetan, O. O., Ige, C. S., & Ike, D. N. (2016). Fiscal decentralization and economic growth in Nigeria: A multivariate co-integration approach. *Journal of Sustainable Development Studies*, 9(2), 243-266.
- Gisore, N., Kiprop, S., Kalio, A., & Ochieng, J. (2014). Effect of government expenditure on economic growth in East Africa: A disaggregated model. *European Journal of Business and Social Sciences*, 3(8), 289-304.
- Haug, E. (2002). *Writings in the margins: Critical reflections on the emerging discourse of international social work*. National Library of Canada= Bibliothèque nationale du Canada.
- Henrekson, M. (1993). The Peacock-Wiseman Hypothesis. In *The Growth of the Public Sector, theories and international evidences*, N. Gemmel (ed.), Cheltenham: Edward Elgar Publishing, 1993.

- Htun, N. M. (2024). Government spending and economic growth: A case study of Myanmar. *Inya Economic Journal*, 3(1), 33-57.
- Iwegbunam, I. A., & Robinson, Z. (2019). Economic growth models and government expenditure in South Africa: A disaggregated impact analysis. *International Journal of Economics and Finance Studies*, 11(1), 33-48.
- Jin, J., & Zou, H. F. (2002). How does fiscal decentralization affect aggregate, national, and subnational government size?. *Journal of Urban Economics*, 52(2), 270-293.
- Lamaritina, S., & Zaghini, A. (2011). Increasing public expenditures: Wagner's law in OECD countries. *German Economic Review*, 12(2), 149-164.
- Levin, A., Lin, C. F., & Chu, C. S. J. (2002). Unit root tests in panel data: asymptotic and finite-sample properties. *Journal of Econometrics*, 108(1), 1-24.
- Lucas, R. E. (1986). On the mechanics of economic development. *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 22(1), 3-42. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-3932\(88\)90168-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-3932(88)90168-7)
- Nyasha, S., & Odhiambo, N. M. (2019). Government size and economic growth: A review of international literature. *Sage Open*, 9(3), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.2158244019877200>.
- Okunlola, O. C., Sani, I. U., Ayetigbo, O. A., & Oyadeyi, O. O. (2024). Effect of government expenditure on real economic growth in ECOWAS: assessing the moderating role of corruption and conflict. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 11(1), 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-024-03285-x>
- Olaoye, O. O., Eluwole, O. O., Ayesha, A., & Afolabi, O. O. (2020). Government spending and economic growth in ECOWAS: An asymmetric analysis. *The Journal of Economic Asymmetries*, 22, e00180. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeca.2020.e00180>
- Olaoye, O. O., Orisadare, M., Okorie, U. U., & Abanikanda, E. (2020). Re-examining the government expenditure-growth nexus in ECOWAS countries. *Journal of Economic and Administrative Sciences*, 36(4), 277-301. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEAS-12-2018-0140>
- Olayiwola, W. K., & Osabuohien, E. S. (2010). Evaluation of the role of fiscal policy in promoting savings, investment and capital formation in Nigeria. *The Journal of Banking and Finance*, 10(1), 26-45.
- Olulu, R. M., Erhieyovwe, E. K., & Andrew, U. (2014). Government expenditures and economic growth: The Nigerian experience. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(10), 89-94. <https://doi.org/10.5901/mjss.2014.v5n10p89>
- Onifade, S. T., Çevik, S., Erdoğan, S., Asongu, S., & Bekun, F. V. (2020). An empirical retrospect of the impacts of government expenditures on economic growth: new

- evidence from the Nigerian economy. *Journal of Economic Structures*, 9(1), 6. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40008-020-0186-7>
- Osasona, A. V., Oluniluyi, A. E., & Ayorinde, B. F. (2024). Impact of government expenditure on economic growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Arts, Languages and Business Studies*, 12, 1-11.
- Peacock, A. T., & Wiseman, J. (1961). Determinants of government expenditure. NBER Chapters, in: *The Growth of Public Expenditure in the United Kingdom: 12-34* National Bureau of Economic Research, Inc.
- Pesaran, M. H., Shin, Y., & Smith, R. J. (2001). Bounds testing approaches to the analysis of level relationships. *Journal of Applied Econometrics*, 16(3), 289-326. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jae.616>
- Pesaran, M., & Shin, Y. (1999). *An autoregressive distributed lag modeling approach to cointegration analysis*. Department of Applied Economics, University of Cambridge.
- Poku, K., Opoku, E., & Agyeiwaa Ennin, P. (2022). The influence of government expenditure on economic growth in Ghana: An Ardl approach. *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23322039.2022.2160036>
- Pula, L., & Elshani, A. (2018). Role of public expenditure in economic growth: Econometric evidence from Kosovo 2002–2015. *Baltic Journal of Real Estate Economics and Construction Management*, 6, 74-87.
- Rahman, M., Nath, S., Siddiqui, M., & Hossain, S. (2023) The impact of government expenditure on economic growth: A study of SAARC countries. *Open Journal of Business and Management*, 11, 1691-1703. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ojbm.2023.114095>
- Ram, R. (1986). Government size and economic growth: A new framework and some evidence from cross-section and time-series data. *American Economic Review*, 76, 191-203.
- Rodden, J. (2003). Reviving Leviathan: Fiscal federalism and the growth of government. *International Organization*, 57, 695-729.
- Romer, P. M. (1986). Increasing returns and long-run growth. *Journal of Political Economy*, 94, 1002-1037.
- Rubinson, R. (1977). Dependency, government revenue and economic growth, 1955-1970. *Studies in Comparative International Development*, 12, 3-28.
- Shaari, M. S., Masnan, F., Abd Rani, M. J., Zainal Abidin, Z., Ridzuan, A. R., & Othman, N. (2023). The grim cost of economic growth and environmental degradation: A comprehensive panel ARDL study of public debt in the ASEAN-5 countries. *Sustainability*, 15(14), 10756. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15141>

- Srithongrung, A., & Kriz, K. A. (2014). The impact of subnational fiscal policies on economic growth: A dynamic analysis approach. *Journal of Policy Analysis and Management*, 33(4), 912-928.
- Srithongrung, A., & Sánchez-Juárez, I. (2015). Fiscal policies and subnational economic growth in Mexico. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues*, 5(1), 11-22.
- Sungchan, K., & Soyoung, P. (2020). The effectiveness of capital expenditure in an endogenous growth model: Evidence from US states. *International Journal of Economics and Business Research*, 19(4), 378-390.
- Udude, C. C., Amadi, A. O., & Amadi, A. (2023). Re-evaluation of government expenditure on economic growth in Nigeria. *South East Journal of Political Science*, 9(2), 304-316.
- Yusuf, S. A., Babalola, B., Aninkan, O. D. & Salako, M. A. (2015). Analysis of impact of sectoral government expenditures on economic growth in Nigeria: Bound test co-integration approach. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 7(12), 171-184.

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